

1 **Simulating the effects of wind and snow damage on the optimal**
2 **management of Norwegian spruce forests**

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14

15 **Abstract**

16 Overlooking the risk of wind and snow damage in forest planning may lead to
17 suboptimal management prescriptions. In this study, we analysed the optimal
18 management of an even-aged, spruce-dominated stand in Norway under the risk of
19 snow and wind damage. The management aim was to maximise discounted net
20 revenues of timber production. We used a simulation-optimisation system based on
21 models for stand dynamics and damage, considering risk using a deterministic and
22 stochastic approach. The different approaches to simulating damage resulted in 41
23 optimisation cases. The results show that considering risk leads to earlier cuttings,
24 lower growing stock densities towards the end of the rotations and changes in the
25 number and intensity of thinnings. The inclusion of stochastic damage provided a
26 valid approach for considering the uncertainty associated with the risk of damage.
27 Ignoring the effect of wind and snow damage in the calculations resulted in an
28 overestimation of the revenues by up to 25%. The results from this study will help to
29 integrate the risk of natural disturbances into forestry decision-making, and provide a
30 better understanding of the implications snow and wind damage have on optimal
31 forest management.

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34 **Keywords:** Risk management, forest management, hazards, natural disturbances,
35 differential evolution, optimisation, boreal forest.

36

37 **1. Introduction**

38

39 Forests are facing an increasingly uncertain future due to natural disturbances and
40 changes in their regimes (Linder et al., 2010; Seidl et al., 2017). Increasing
41 uncertainty due to disturbances has been linked to climate change, variation in
42 forests' interactions with disturbances, lack of knowledge on the anthropogenic
43 suppression of disturbances, and the introduction of invasive species (O'Hara and
44 Ramage, 2013). As a result, disturbances, and their ecological impacts on forests,
45 have been put at the forefront in several studies (e.g. González-Olabarria et al.,
46 2008; Pukkala et al., 2016; Seidl et al., 2017).

47

48 Snow and wind disturbances are a common cause of damage in forests (Valinger
49 and Fridman, 2011; Mitchell, 2013) that must be addressed in forest planning. Such
50 disturbances not only have significant ecological effects on forest biodiversity,
51 creating new habitats and modifying the forest carbon balance (Bellone et al., 2017;
52 Zubizarreta-Gerendiain et al., 2017), but also represent an economic threat
53 (Gardiner et al., 2013). Snow and wind damage lead to the unplanned harvesting of
54 trees or to a decision to leave damaged trees unharvested, thus changing the
55 original management plans, and reducing economic revenues and the provision of
56 forest products or services (Gadow, 2000). If the aim is to anticipate the delivery of
57 forest services or economic revenues with acceptable certainty (or with high
58 probability), we need tools to integrate risk into the planning of forest management
59 prescriptions, which will become increasingly relevant in the coming decades (Seidl
60 et al., 2017).

61

62 Although the extent to which climate change will affect the occurrence of snow and
63 wind patterns in boreal forests is currently unclear (Mölter et al., 2016), we can
64 nevertheless address the effect of considering these risks on management (Gadow,
65 2000). Risk can be considered in forest management by either developing
66 prescriptions that enhance the resistance and resilience of forests, or by anticipating
67 the outputs of forestry under alternative risk scenarios, and using those estimations
68 to select management options that could minimise potential losses.

69

70 One approach to developing forest management alternatives that include risk is to
71 use a computational representation of the forest system (e.g. Valinger and Fridman,
72 1999). Forest dynamics are simulated with models created using empirically
73 collected data (Seidl, 2016). Through simulations, we are able to produce detailed
74 representations of forest dynamics, and obtain results that were not assessed when
75 the forest dynamics were modelled (Winsberg, 2010). For example, we can
76 investigate the effect of completely new management options on the desired forest
77 functions, such as the effect that changes in thinning intensity or rotation length will
78 have on forest production. When forest dynamics are simulated with one of the
79 processes being stochastic, the simulation provides a range of possible outcomes.
80 As a result, the manager can analyse the risks and uncertainty associated with
81 alternative management options (Pukkala and Kangas, 1996; González-Olabarria et
82 al., 2017; Zubizarreta-Gerendiain et al., 2017).

83

84 Finding the optimal management strategy under uncertain circumstances is a
85 complex task, as it requires the consideration of multiple variables and sources.

86 These uncertainties might result from future changes in harvesting costs and prices

87 (Leskinen and Kangas, 1998; Pukkala and Kellomäki, 2012), management
88 objectives or various biotic and abiotic risks (Heinonen et al., 2009). Under such
89 circumstances, the management aim might be to minimise risk (Heinonen et al.,
90 2009), to see the effect of risk considerations on optimal management (e.g. with
91 timber production as the main objective; Zeng et al., 2007), to maximise the
92 expected timber revenues under risk, to increase forest resilience or to create less
93 vulnerable forest structures (Zubizarreta-Gerendiain et al., 2017).

94

95 The selection of an optimal management that considers risk is preceded by
96 estimation of the loss caused by potential damage versus the cost of action to
97 prevent the damage (Hanewinkel et al., 2011). These estimations are done using
98 models that predict the probability and degree of damage. In Norway, there have
99 been studies on the optimal management strategies for steady timber production at
100 the regional level (Hofstad, 1991), timber production potential at the country level
101 (Hoen et al., 2001; Eid et al., 2002) and optimal management considering carbon
102 flows (Raymer et al., 2009; Buongiorno et al., 2012). However, none of the previous
103 studies have included the risk of damage due to abiotic agents such as snow and
104 wind in the optimisation of stand management, even though wind and snow
105 disturbances are a common cause of damage in Norway (Díaz-Yáñez et al., 2016).

106

107 This study has developed and demonstrated an approach to integrating snow and
108 wind damage into forestry decision-making. It also analysed the implications of the
109 risk of damage and the effect of uncertain costs or prices on optimal management.

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112 **2. Material and methods**

113

114 2.1. Stand dynamics simulation

115

116 Different models were used to simulate forest dynamics (Table 1), consisting of tree
117 growth, recruitment and mortality. Additional models were employed to calculate tree
118 height, biomass and volume. The risk of wind and snow damage was calculated
119 using predictive damage models (Figure 1).

120

121 *About here Table 1*

122

123 *About here Figure 1*

124

125 The simulation of growth and forest regeneration was based on the models of
126 Bollandsås et al. (2008). These models predict the 5-year diameter growth of a tree
127 and the expected number of recruits. All the recruited new trees were assigned a
128 diameter of 5 cm, as all the ingrowth models were developed for a 5-cm-diameter
129 limit. The simulation was done at tree level, using representative trees; that is, each
130 tree represented a certain number of trees per ha. A representative tree was
131 removed from the simulation when it represented fewer than 0.5 trees per ha.

132

133 A limitation of the mortality model of Bollandsås et al. (2008), from the point of view
134 of our study, was the lack of information concerning the cause of mortality.

135 Therefore, it was not possible to tell how much of the predicted mortality was due to
136 competition and how much was due to damage. Because we used separate models

137 for damage, we fitted a new model for competition-induced over each five-year
138 period, using the same predictors as in the original model of Bollandsås et al. (2008)
139 (see supplementary material). The dataset consisted of trees present in plots with no
140 disturbance records, according to the Norwegian National Forest Inventory (NFI)
141 protocols (Landsskogtakseringens, 2008). The data were obtained from the 8th, 9th
142 and 10th NFIs. All the predictors had to be significant at the 0.05 level, and the
143 residuals had to indicate a non-biased model. To assess the performance of the
144 fitted models, the area under the receiver operating characteristic curve was
145 calculated (often referred to as AUC).

146

147 The tree heights were estimated for each 5-year period during the simulation by
148 using the ordinary least square models of Sharma and Breidenbach (2014). These
149 models use the tree diameter at breast height (DBH) as the predictor. The individual
150 tree heights were then used to calculate the mean height predictor of the damage
151 models (Díaz-Yáñez et al. 2017). The damage models were constructed using the
152 mean height estimates available in the NFI datasets (Landsskogtakseringens, 2008)
153 and therefore did not use the Sharma and Breidenbach (2014) models. We noticed
154 that there was a systematic difference between the mean stand heights calculated
155 using the height models and the mean estimates available in the NFI datasets
156 (based on NFI observations). Therefore, in the estimation of damage, we used a
157 correction factor to calibrate the mean height estimates to those used in the damage
158 models.

159

160 The tree volumes were estimated using existing models: Vestjordet (1967) for
161 spruce, Braastad (1967) for pine and Braastad (1966) for birch and other

162 broadleaves. These models predict the stem volume under bark, based on DBH and
163 tree height.

164

165 The initial stand conditions for the simulation (Table 2) were based on a randomly
166 selected plot from the NFI data (8th, 9th and 10th NFIs) representing spruce-
167 dominated forest. The pool from which this initial plot was selected was restricted to:
168 1) well-stocked young stands with more than 1500 trees ha⁻¹, corresponding to the
169 youngest development classes, according to the NFI protocols
170 (Landsskogtakseringens, 2008); 2) productive forest land; 3) those with an absence
171 of silvicultural treatments in the past 5 years; and 4) location within the 25% and 75%
172 thresholds (expressed as quartiles from the distribution of young spruce stands)
173 concerning slope, altitude and latitude (Table 2).

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175 *About here Table 2*

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177

178 2.2. Risk simulation

179

180 The models predicting snow and wind damage occurrence at the tree (Díaz-Yáñez et
181 al., 2017) and stand (Díaz-Yáñez et al., 2018) levels included both site variables
182 (latitude or altitude) and stand variables (stand density, mean diameter, mean
183 height). The rate of snow and wind damage was predicted from stand basal area,
184 mean tree height, mean diameter and average slenderness of the trees. The models
185 were different for uprooted and broken trees. The damage probabilities obtained
186 from the models of Díaz-Yáñez et al. (2018) were converted to 5-year probabilities.

187 The predicted damage was assigned to different diameters following the observed
188 diameter distributions of damaged trees by dominant stand species (see
189 supplementary material).

190

191 Damage was simulated by both deterministic and stochastic approaches (Figure 2).

192 In the deterministic approach, the predicted probability of the stand to be damaged

193 (damage occurrence) was multiplied by the predicted probability of any tree in the

194 stand to be uprooted and broken (damage rate). The resulting value was multiplied

195 by the number of remaining trees in the stand to obtain the number of damaged

196 trees. In the stochastic approach, randomness was simulated (1) at plot level and (2)

197 at both plot and tree level. The stochastic damage was simulated by comparing the

198 predicted probability of damage to a random number drawn from a binomial

199 distribution. In addition, we analysed the impact of applying fixed probabilities for

200 damage occurrence at the stand-level (deterministic damage). The 5-year

201 probabilities were 0.2, 0.5 and 0.8, referred to as low, medium and high probability of

202 damage, respectively.

203

204 *About here Figure 2*

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206 We also calculated the uncertainty associated with each of four optimal management

207 schedules – 1) no damage, 2) deterministic damage, 3) stochastic damage at plot

208 level, and 4) stochastic damage at plot and tree level – by simulating them 6000

209 times with stochastic damage at the plot and tree levels. The four optimal

210 management schedules were developed with average stand establishment cost

211 (1500 EUR ha⁻¹) and a 2% discount rate.

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2.3 Economic parameters

The timber values were calculated from the estimated pulpwood and sawn wood proportions of the harvested trees. The pulpwood proportion was estimated using the equations developed for spruce and pine (Blingsmo and Veidahl, 1992) and assuming that 80% of the birch and other broadleaf volume went to pulpwood production (and the remaining 20% was left in the forest). The equations from Blingsmo and Veidahl (1992) assumed perfect trees, and therefore wood waste was not considered. We imposed a diameter limit of 13 cm, assuming that smaller trees did not provide any revenue. We also set a maximum limit of 60 cm (capacity limit of sawmills), beyond which all the volume was pulpwood. The average prices per m³ were obtained from Statistics Norway (2017), collected in 2016 for spruce, pine and broadleaves/birch. The average sawn wood prices were 50.56, 48.77 and, 32.47 EUR m⁻³, and the average pulpwood prices were 23.4, 21.4 and, 24.4 EUR m⁻³ for spruce, pine and birch, respectively.

Harvesting and forwarding costs were calculated using the productivity functions from Dale et al. (1993) and Dale and Stamm (1994) (Table 3), assuming 100 EUR h⁻¹ in forwarding and 156 EUR h⁻¹ in harvesting, following Bergseng et al. (2013). We applied an adjusted time by slope, following Bergseng et al. (2013). The equation for transport productivity (h m⁻³) presented in Dale and Stamm (1994) was based on the forwarding distance. We assumed a distance to road of 692 m (mean forwarding distance; Antón-Fernández and Astrup, 2012) and a volume per load of 15 m³. The

237 total costs of harvesting and forwarding were constrained within a reasonable range:
238 in thinning, between 8 and 20 EUR m⁻³, and for clear felling, between 5 and 15 EUR
239 m⁻³. A fixed cost of 100 EUR per cutting was also included.

240

241 The economic outcomes of the management schedules depend on discount rate
242 (opportunity cost), stand establishment costs and timber prices, all of which are
243 uncertain variables. To assess their impact on optimal management, we performed a
244 sensitivity analysis for each of them, where the stand establishment costs were
245 1000, 1500 and 2000 EUR ha⁻¹, the discount rates were 1, 2 and 3% and the timber
246 prices were increased or decreased by 20% compared to the baseline prices given
247 above.

248

249

250 2.4 Optimisation

251 The objective of the optimisation was to maximise the economic revenue using the
252 land expectation value (LEV) depending on decision variables and variables subject
253 to uncertainty. The decision variables, or controlled factors, defined the management
254 schedule. The purpose of optimisation was to identify the optimal even-aged
255 management regime, including decisions on the length of the rotation and the
256 thinning regime. The LEV is the present value per unit area (EUR ha⁻¹), assuming a
257 sequence of even-aged forest rotations identical to the first rotation.

258 In order to calculate the LEV, we first estimated the net present value for the first
259 rotation (R_1) (Equation 1).

260

261

262 (Eq. 1)

$$263 \quad NPV_{R_1} = -C_0 + \sum_{t=1}^{R-1} \frac{\sum P_{it}Y_{it} - C_t}{(1+r)^t} + \frac{\sum P_{pR}Y_{pR} - C_R}{(1+r)^R}$$

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265

266 The first term of Equation 1, $-C_0$, corresponds to the stand establishment costs. The
267 second term is the sum of the present values of the intermediate costs, C_t , and
268 revenues, $P_{it}Y_{it}$, in each year, t , where Y_{it} is the yield (the timber volume cut in the
269 thinning) by species and assortment, i , and P_{it} is the timber price for each species
270 and assortment, i . The term r is the discount rate. The last term corresponds to the
271 present value of the final clear fell (at rotation time R).

272

273 After calculating the net present value (NPV) of the first rotation, the NPV_{R_1} was
274 converted into land expectation value by applying the following formula for infinite
275 periodic payment:

276

277 (Eq. 2)

$$278 \quad LEV = \frac{(1+r)^R NPV_{R_1}}{(1+r)^R - 1}$$

279

280 Management was optimised by determining the best combination of decision
281 variables: thinning years, rotation length, thinning intensities and thinning type.
282 Thinning intensities and type were calculated using a thinning intensity curve
283 (Pukkala et al., 2014; Pukkala, 2015; Jin et al., 2017). This curve defines the
284 proportion of harvested trees of a certain diameter. The curve has two parameters,
285 which define the type and intensity of thinning. In summary, the optimised variables

286 were: number of five-year intervals between initial age and the first thinning; between
287 subsequent thinnings (maximum of five thinnings) and between the last thinning and
288 final harvest; and the parameters of the thinning intensity curve for each thinning.

289

290 For the optimisation, we used differential evolution, a population-based method
291 which has previously shown good results (Arias-Rodil et al., 2015). This technique
292 uses a population of solution vectors that include the values of decision variables.
293 Different solution vectors are combined to create new solution vectors. If a new
294 solution vector is good in terms of the LEV, it replaces one of the previous solution
295 vectors. This process is continued for several iterations, and the best solution vector
296 after the final iteration is taken as the optimal solution. A more detailed description of
297 the algorithm is presented in Pukkala (2009). Based on preliminary analyses, we
298 used 50 solution vectors as the population size and 50 iterations. The other
299 parameter values of differential evolution were the ones recommended in Jin et al.
300 (2018).

301

302 Several penalties and restrictions were used in the optimisation process (Table 3).

303 The penalty functions were strong enough to prevent illogical solutions and

304 extrapolation beyond the ranges of the models, with:

305

- 306 • The simulation being run for a maximum of 205 years, but with a penalty
307 function being applied when the simulation length was over 100 years.
- 308 • Thinning intensity being penalised when the proportion of removed basal area
309 was above 0.7.
- 310 • Thinnings being restricted to stands with mean diameters above 13 cm.

- 311 • A penalty being applied for rotations shorter than 50 years.
- 312 • A minimum interval of 5 years between cuttings, being consistent with the
- 313 projection period of the growth simulator.

314

315 *Table 3 about here*

316

317

318 **3. Results**

319

320 The inclusion of snow and wind risk had an effect on the optimal management
321 strategy (Figure 3). Considering risk either shortened or maintained rotation, keeping
322 it equal for most of the optimisation cases. Increasing discount rates meant a
323 decrease in the stand basal area and a shorter rotation length. The growing stock
324 volume was lower with risk, especially towards the end of the rotation.

325

326 *Figure 3 about here*

327

328 Among the management schedules that were optimised under risk, the mean volume
329 losses were $0.25 \text{ m}^3 \text{ ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$, with a standard deviation of 0.29 (mean of the 27
330 optimal schedules, excluding the options that modified the probability of occurrence
331 and prices). Simulating the optimal management obtained without considering the
332 risk of damage overestimated the LEVs. The maximum overestimation occurred
333 when the stand establishment cost was 2000 EUR ha^{-1} and the discount rate was
334 2%; in this case, the differences in the LEV, with and without risk, were 25%.

335

336 Increasing damage occurrence meant a reduction in the rotation length when using
337 the baseline parameters (stand establishment costs of 1500 EUR ha⁻¹ and a 2%
338 discount rate) and a deterministic approach to consider risk (Figure 4). The results
339 showed that setting the 5-year probability of snow and wind risk occurrence at 0.2
340 gave a similar optimal management as obtained when the risk was predicted using
341 the models. On the other hand, when the probability of damage occurrence was set
342 at a higher level, the optimal management changed: at 0.5, one thinning was applied
343 and the rotation length was 75 years, and at 0.8, the damage was equal to the basal
344 area growth in the stand.

345

346 *About here Figure 4*

347

348 Changing timber prices (Figure 5) and stand establishment costs (Figure 6) affected
349 the optimal management. Considering risk using the deterministic approach and by
350 reducing prices by 20% resulted in a longer rotation length, and increasing the prices
351 by 20% reduced the rotation length. Higher stand establishment costs delayed
352 investment in the next tree generation, making the rotation longer. Management
353 considering risk tended to have lower stand volumes. This was most visible when the
354 stand establishment costs were 1500 EUR ha⁻¹.

355

356 *About here Figure 5*

357

358 *About here Figure 6*

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360 Each management schedule had a certain degree of uncertainty as a result of
361 stochastic damage. Figure 7 shows four different optimal management prescriptions
362 with their associated uncertainty. For management considering risk with a
363 deterministic approach, the 95% confidence limits of the LEV are 890–1110 EUR ha⁻¹
364 ¹. The difference between the mean value obtained from considering risk with a
365 deterministic approach and the optimal management without considering damage
366 was 3.2%.

367

368 *About here Figure 7*

369

370 **4. Discussion**

371

372 Addressing the effects of wind and snow damage in forest management is a complex
373 task that requires appropriate methodological approaches. However, ignoring the
374 effect of damage in management results in overestimated revenues and suboptimal
375 management, as shown by our results and in other studies (e.g. Zubizarreta-
376 Gerendiain et al., 2017).

377

378 Our simulations showed that considering the risk of snow and wind damage tends to
379 shorten the optimal rotation period, as suggested by earlier studies, where longer
380 rotations tend to increase damage (e.g. Wallentin and Nilsson, 2014). In those cases
381 where the rotation length was longer when considering damage, the optimal
382 management approach included a greater number of thinnings or greater thinning
383 intensity, which would explain why the rotation length was longer. Our study only
384 considered timber production. If we included other ecosystem services, such as

385 biodiversity and carbon, it is likely that the effect of risk on the rotation length would
386 be different (Liski et al., 2001).

387

388 Management considering the risk of snow and wind damage tends to have lower
389 growing stock volumes towards the end of the rotation; increasing discount rate
390 (higher opportunity costs for standing trees) had a similar effect. When the stand was
391 managed under risk, it was better to remove trees earlier and decrease stand density
392 when the trees were economically valuable. The same effect has previously been
393 observed when optimising management under the risk of fire (González-Olabarria et
394 al., 2008).

395

396 Considering the effect of disturbances with a deterministic approach does not fully
397 describe the uncertainty associated with the management schedule. We need the
398 mean values of the disturbance effects, but also their variation in order to better
399 evaluate the impact of the disturbance (McCarthy and Burgman, 1995). The use of
400 the stochastic approach reflected this variation, which is more informative for
401 adaptive management, and makes it possible to consider the risk attitudes of the
402 forest landowner. Whereas a risk-averse landowner might prefer less variation, the
403 risk-taker would select management options with greater variation that may result in
404 high revenues with low probability, under exceptionally favourable states of nature.

405

406 The results showed that the estimated LEV variation was similar for the four optimal
407 schedules, corresponding to the different approaches used to consider risk, when all
408 schedules were simulated many times so that the damage was stochastic. Since the
409 distributions of the LEV were fairly similar for all schedules, it can be concluded that

410 the risk attitude of the decision-maker will not affect the ranking of these four
411 schedules. But even in those cases where the ranges of variation are similar, it is still
412 important to know the associated uncertainties for a more effective risk management
413 (Blennow et al., 2014). In our results, there was an improvement in the mean LEV
414 when using the optimal management that considered risk in optimisation (with a
415 deterministic approach) compared to the management that was optimised without
416 the risk of damage. On the other hand, management based on stochastic
417 optimisation provided lower, or very similar, mean LEV values, probably reflecting
418 that the stochastic simulation of risk resulted in a more complicated optimisation
419 problem, making it more difficult to determine the true optimal solution.

420

421 In this study, we used a simulator specifically created for Norwegian conditions and
422 an optimisation approach to analyse alternative management schemes. The
423 developed simulator presented some advantages over earlier simulators (Eid and
424 Hobbelstad, 2000; Gobakken et al., 2008) in terms of methodological approach, as
425 well as the integration of the most recent models for forest growth (Bolandsås et al.,
426 2008; Sharma and Breidenbach, 2014) and forest damage (Díaz-Yáñez et al., 2017,
427 2018). However, the models used could also be considered to be a limitation, since
428 part of the models were taken from rather old studies.

429

430 For instance, one drawback concerning the estimation of revenues (Blingsmo and
431 Veidahl, 1992) was the use of models that were developed for a timber market
432 situation that may no longer correspond to the current markets. A better alternative
433 would be using current market prices and a taper function for calculating assortment
434 volumes. However, there are no taper models in Norway, and using the functions

435 from other countries may also lead to errors because these models do not
436 necessarily represent Norwegian conditions. Furthermore, timber prices change
437 through time, increasing the uncertainty in management decisions (Leskinen and
438 Kangas, 1998). We took this aspect into consideration by evaluating the effect of
439 changing timber prices on the optimal management. The results showed that a
440 change in timber price had an effect on optimal rotation length.

441

442 In addition to the lack of up-to-date models, the combined use of many models made
443 it difficult to evaluate the reliability of the simulation predictions, due to the
444 propagation of errors. However, correlations of the errors in different models should
445 be known in order to properly simulate variation not explained by the models. These
446 correlations are largely unknown because the models of the simulator were obtained
447 from different studies, and each study reports the residual variation of only one
448 model.

449

450 Concerning the representativeness of the results, the analysis was based on a single
451 stand. The main aim of the selected initial stand was to be representative of spruce-
452 dominated young stands. It is obvious that the structure, location and species
453 composition of the stand will affect the results of the simulations. For instance,
454 latitude, altitude and slope greatly influence both the growth and damage predictions
455 (Bollansås et al., 2008; Díaz-Yáñez et al., 2018). A way to deal with this variation,
456 although beyond the scope of this study, would be to produce a landscape-level
457 analysis using a variety of conditions (Heinonen et al., 2011; Senf and Seidl, 2017).

458

459 Regarding the approach for finding optimal management, previous studies
460 considering risk have used direct search optimisation methods, such as Hooke and
461 Jeeves (González et al., 2005; González-Olabarria et al., 2008; Möykkynen and
462 Pukkala, 2010). Although all the optimisation approaches work adequately, it has
463 been proven that, for more complicated cases where many decision variables are
464 involved, it may be worthwhile using population-based methods, especially
465 differential evolution and particle swarm optimisation (Arias-Rodil et al., 2015; Jin et
466 al., 2018).

467

468 Several clear conclusions can be drawn from this study. Considering risk of damage
469 from snow and wind has management implications, such as shortening rotation
470 lengths, reducing stand density and the value of the growing stock towards the end
471 of the rotation. The current results improve our understanding of stand management
472 under risk, and highlight the importance of considering natural disturbances when
473 making management decisions.

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475

476 **Supplementary material**

477

478 The following supplementary material is available:

479 *Adapted model of mortality due to competition*

480 *Tree level damage as a function of the diameter based on observed values*

481

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500

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Table 1. Stand dynamics models. Subscript *i* and *s* indicate whether the dependent variable is provided for each tree in the stand or at stand level (*i*: tree number 1...*n*; *s*: stand number 1...*N*).

Simulation task	Tree/stand species	Reference	Dependent variable	Independent variables
Tree growth (I)	Norway spruce	Bollandsås et al. (2008)	l_{is} (mm) = Diameter growth of tree <i>i</i> of species <i>s</i> over 5 years	DBH (mm), BAL (m ² ha ⁻¹), SI (m), LAT (degrees and minutes)
	Scots pine	Bollandsås et al. (2008)		
	Birch	Bollandsås et al. (2008)		
	Other broadleaves	Adapted Bollandsås et al. (2008)*		
Tree mortality due to competition (m)	Norway spruce	Adapted Bollandsås et al. (2008)*	m_{is} = Expected probability of death of tree <i>i</i> of species <i>s</i> due to competition over 5 years	DBH (mm), BA (m ² ha ⁻¹),
	Scots pine	Adapted Bollandsås et al. (2008)*		
	Birch	Adapted Bollandsås et al. (2008)*		
	Other broadleaves	Bollandsås et al. (2008)		
Tree recruitment (R)	Norway spruce	Bollandsås et al. (2008)	$R_{s\ sp}$ = Expected number of recruits conditional on positive recruitment for each species <i>sp</i> over 5 years	BA (m ² ha ⁻¹), SI (m), PBA (%)
	Scots pine	Bollandsås et al. (2008)		
	Birch	Bollandsås et al. (2008)		
	Other broadleaves	Bollandsås et al. (2008)		
Tree height (H)	Norway spruce	Sharma and Breidenbach (2014)	$H_{is}(m)$ = Height of tree <i>i</i> of species <i>s</i>	DBH (cm)
	Scots pine	Sharma and Breidenbach (2014)		
	Birch/other broadleaves	Sharma and Breidenbach (2014)		
Tree volume (V)	Norway spruce	Vestjordet (1967)	V_{is} (dm ³) = Tree volume under bark	DBH (mm), H (dm)
	Scots pine	Braastad (1967)		
	Birch/other broadleaves	Braastad (1966)		
Stand damage occurrence probability (Poc)	Norway spruce	Díaz-Yáñez et al. (2018)	Poc _s = Probability of a stand to be damaged by snow and wind	LAT (degrees and minutes), slope (%), soil type (categorical), forest type (categorical), mBAdbh (cm), rhd (m/cm), N (trees ha ⁻¹), Gini, Shannon
	Birch	Díaz-Yáñez et al. (2018)		
	Mixed	Díaz-Yáñez et al. (2018)		
Tree damage rate (uprooted: Pup; broken: Pbr)	Norway spruce	Díaz-Yáñez et al. (2017)	Pup/Pbr _{is} = Probability of tree <i>i</i> of species <i>s</i> in a damaged stand to be uprooted/broken	BA (m ² ha ⁻¹), mdbh (cm), mH (m), Gini, Shannon, rhd (m cm ⁻¹), birch (%)
	Birch	Díaz-Yáñez et al. (2017)		
	Mixed	Díaz-Yáñez et al. (2017)		

(*): A new model was constructed, for details see the supplementary material.

DBH: diameter at breast height; BAL: basal area of the trees larger than the tree of interest; SI: site index; LAT: latitude; BA: basal area; PBA: percentage of basal area for the subject species; mBAdbh: mean diameter by basal area; rhd: slenderness; mdbh: mean diameter; mH: mean height.

Table 2. Characteristics of the initial selected plot for the simulation compared to typical, young, well-stocked spruce stands with respect to basal area (BA), density, slope, latitude and altitude, based on the data available from the Norwegian NFI from the 8th–10th inventories.

	Selected		All plots		
	plot	mean	SD	min	max
BA (m ² ha ⁻¹)	14.5	13.8	6.1	0.2	29.8
Density (trees ha ⁻¹)	1840	1915	322.9	40	2920
Slope (%)	23	20.91	14.36	1	99
Latitude (x 10 ⁵ m)	67.8 N	68.3 N	2.13	64.6 N	76.6 N
Altitude (m)	705	453.45	232.45	10	1010

Table 3. Models used for the economic evaluation, with the restrictions or penalties applied to them.

Simulation task	Reference	Dependent variable	Independent variables	Optimised variables	Restrictions/penalties
Thinning intensity	Pukkala et al. (2014), Pukkala (2015), Jin et al. (2017)	ThinP _{is} (%) = proportion of trees that would be cut for each tree type	DBH (cm)	Parameter a1 and a2 of the thinning intensity curve □	Thinning intensity is not applied to those stands with mean dbh < 13cm. There is a penalty for thinnings above 70% of the basal area.
Price	Blingsmo and Veidahl (1992)	PropPulp (%) = proportion of pulpwood	DBH (mm), H(dm)	None	The valid area of the function is D=130–450 mm and H=140–280 dm. Trees with diameters above 60 cm do not produce sawn wood. Trees below 13 cm diameter do not provide any revenue.
Harvesting and forwarding costs	Dale et al. (1993), Dale and Stamm (1994)	HarvProd (m ³ h ⁻¹)	V (m ³): average harvested tree volume size in the stand U (%): percentage of removed trees D (trees ha ⁻¹): stand density	None	Combined harvesting and forwarding costs were restricted to 8–20 EUR m ⁻³ in thinnings and 5–15 EUR m ⁻³ in clear cuts.

Figure 1. Structure of the simulation-optimisation system

Figure 2. Description of risk considered during the simulation. \widehat{P}_{oc} is the predicted probability of damage occurrence at stand level, following Díaz-Yáñez et al. (2018); \widehat{P}_{up} and \widehat{P}_{br} are the predicted damage probabilities of any tree in the stand to be uprooted and broken, following Díaz-Yáñez et al. (2017); N is the total number of live trees in the stand; $P_{n\ up\ prop}$ and $P_{n\ br\ prop}$ are the proportions of damaged trees for each representative tree in the stand based on the observed damage distribution $P_{n\ up\ DC}$ and $P_{n\ br\ DC}$; and D_{up} and D_{br} are the total number of trees damaged for each representative tree.

Figure 3. Optimal rotation length and basal area dynamics across time for 1%, 2% and 3% discount rate, stand establishment costs of 1500 EUR ha⁻¹, baseline timber prices and considering the risk of damage using four different approaches: 1) no risk of wind and snow damage (*No damage*); 2) deterministic simulation of damage (*Damage*); 3) stochastic simulation of damage at plot and tree level (*Stochastic (pt)*); and 4) only at plot level (*Stochastic (p)*).

Figure 4. Effect of the probability of the occurrence of risk damage on optimal management when the stand establishment costs are 1500 EUR ha⁻¹ and the discount rate is 2%. The lines represent the optimal management with a deterministic simulation of risk with three occurrence probabilities: low (0.2), medium (0.5) and high (0.8).

Figure 5. Effect of changes in the timber prices on management when the stand establishment costs are 1500 EUR ha⁻¹ and the discount rate is 2%. The lines represent the optimal management with a deterministic risk simulation.

Figure 6. Effect of changes in stand establishment costs on optimal management for a 2% discount rate. The lines represent the optimal management considering the risk of damage with four different approaches (see Figure 3).

Figure 7. Distribution of LEV (land expectation value) when the risk is considered stochastic at plot and tree level for the four optimal management schedules obtained using four different approaches to consider risk (calculated with a 2% discount rate and 1500 EUR ha⁻¹ of stand establishment costs).